

THE DISADAPTATION OF ADOLESCENTS IN FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS AND ITS PREVENTION

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Abstract

This article discusses the reasons of the disadaptation in adolescents' behavior and its occurrence in family relationships. Moreover, some ways of prevention from disadaptation of adolescents are given.

Key words: adaptation, disadaptation, maladjustment, parental warmth, family, relationship, adulthood, external, internal

The family is the fundamental unit where the socialization of the child is carried out. Of all the defects in the socialization of the individual, the most dangerous are family defects. The process of socialization in the family involves the assimilation by the child of models of normative, socially approved behavior of parents. Their behavior up to a certain age becomes a standard for imitation. Knowledge of parental norms-models and patterns of behavior allows the teenager not to look for new solutions in standard situations, but to behave as if automatically, in accordance with the patterns accepted in the given environment and learned by the individual.

Social adaptation is a process and at the same time the result of internal and external harmonization of the individual with the environment, the process of active adaptation of the individual, balancing the needs of a person and the requirements of the environment. Indicators of human adaptation are its balanced relationships with other people, success in activities, harmony in behavior. If this does not happen, the person begins to disadaptation. We believe that: "Disadaptation is the result of internal or external (sometimes complex) deharmonization of the interaction of the individual with himself and society, appearing in internal discomfort, disturbances in the activity, behavior and relationships of the individual, or such behavior of the individual that deharmonizes relations in society, causing moral and material damage". Thus, this is a phenomenon that covers all the difficulties of a person, and in relation to adolescents, all the internal and external difficulties of a given age, regardless of the source of nature and the degree of manifestation.

Disadaptation is a multifactorial process. We have undertaken an analysis of the leading factors that determine the emergence, development of the form and depth of disadaptation. Currently, a significant amount of information has been accumulated on the factors of disadaptation of adolescents, it is required to generalize and systematize it. Disadaptation can be initiated by various factors that can be combined into two main groups: social, or objective, and personal, or subjective. The factors are closely interconnected, complementing and conditioning each other, just as the processes of socio- and psycho-ontogenesis are interconnected. In the first place among the factors determining the level of maladjustment is the family factor. This factor is considered by the vast majority of researchers to be the leading one. One of the leading functions of the family is educational, ensuring the socialization of children. However, the performance of this function is far from always satisfactory, which leads to disadaptation of family members in general and adolescents in particular. If we analyze the period of adolescence, it is a period of life during which autonomy-related changes are negotiated between parents and adolescents, and parent-child conflict increases. The level of conflict varies among families as a function of prior family relationships, family structure, and individual parent and child characteristics.

Researchers identify a number of reasons for disadaptation that occur in the family:

- incomplete family composition, this often leads to an increase in the complex of inferiority, inferiority, depression, neurotic states, anger, premature fulfillment by adolescents of "adult social roles" - breadwinners of families, defenders and others;
- low level of pedagogical culture of parents, leading to hyper-care, or to under-care (according to the classification of A.E. Lichko);
- negative relationships within the family, which determine the increased anxiety of adolescents; frustration and neurotic states; aggressiveness of behavioral reactions, negativism;
- different pedagogical approaches of parents and older relatives;
- removal of parents from the upbringing process for various reasons;
- low or super-secure financial situation of the family, which gives rise to negative patterns of behavior in terms of their impact on adolescents.

Both the occurrence of disadaptation and the strengthening of maladaptation processes due to other factors are associated with family relationships. The most important reason for disadaptation is character traits. Their importance in science has been underestimated for a long time, however, studies by foreign psychologists, a number of domestic scientists S.A. Badmaev, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, A.E. Lichko, S.L. Rubinshtein showed that many cases of disadjustment are caused precisely by violations in the personal sphere. Features of character (its accentuation), according to S.A. Badmaev, may be predisposing factors for the development of neurotic reactions, nerves, etc., causing manifestations of maladaptive behavior.

The effect of increasing disadaptation is usually associated with incorrect reactions of parents to learning failures, individual actions of adolescents, teachers' comments, etc. As a result of subsequent punishment of adolescents, stable maladaptation processes are formed in them, the manifestations of which are different:

- leaving home, which may be caused by fear of physical punishment, or as a response to it;
- joining antisocial groups;
- depressive disorders, which in adolescence at the stage of primary socialization can lead to severe forms of maladaptation, which are often almost irreversible;
- the acquisition of bad habits (alcoholism, drug addiction, substance abuse);
- suicide attempts.

The study of the family factor causes significant difficulties due to the difficulty of penetrating the essence of family relations, determining the type of family, microclimate, hidden motives, and a family leader. Therefore, the methods of indirect study of the family are the most common, although there are also direct surveys, tests and conversations. At first, it is necessary to obtain purely formal information about the family: composition, financial situation, parental education, distribution of responsibilities, and then move on to moral family values, areas of life, spending free time, incentives and punishments, the nature of communication, the style and tone of family relations. Ten types of families with different educational potential are differentiated:

- educational - strong - the proportion of such families in the number of surveyed is 15-20%, the educational environment is close to optimal. Its main feature is the high moral atmosphere of the family;
- educational - stable - this type of family creates generally favorable opportunities for education, and the shortcomings that arise in the family are overcome with the help of other institutions of socialization, primarily schools;
- educational - unstable - this type of family creates generally favorable opportunities. This type of family is characterized by an incorrect pedagogical position of the parents, which, nevertheless, is evened out due to the relatively high educational potential of the family.
- educational - weak - with the loss of social contact (family) with children and control over them. Families where parents, for various reasons, are not able to properly raise children, have lost control over their behavior, yielding their influence to the society of peers;
- educational - conflict - with a constant conflict atmosphere;
- with an aggressive-conflict atmosphere;
- marginal families with alcohol and sexual degradation;
- delinquent;
- criminal;
- mentally burdened .

All these factors have a great impact of adults' lifestyle and their psychological well-beings in a negative way. However, both parental warmth and parental knowledge of adolescent activities affect the overall psychological adaptation of adolescents. Numerous studies have shown that adolescents whose parents transmit warmth and care relationships with their children tend to have lower levels of depression mood. parental warmth is also negatively associated with various adolescent behavior problems such as antisocial behavior, school misconduct and status violations among teenagers of different ethnic and cultural backgrounds. Studies have shown that negative life events affect psychological adaptation of adolescents through their negative impact on quality of interaction between parents and adolescents.

A study of the problem of disadaptation of adolescents showed that in the conditions of instability in the development of society, the processes of

disadaptation of adolescents are sharply rising, associated with an increase in family poverty, alcoholism and drug addiction, an increase in homelessness and neglect of minors, and an increase in juvenile delinquency. The development of a network of social and rehabilitation institutions for working with families and adults contributes to the creation of a system for the prevention of disadaptation of adolescents. Close relationships between parents and adolescents, good parenting skills, joint family activities and positive parenting role modeling has a well-documented impact on adolescent health and development. These are also areas where parents can choose to make positive changes for their children, and where social policy can help parents make those changes.

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